

Studies on Some Soluble Palladium(II) Chelates in Aqueous Solution. Part II. Chelate Formation between Palladium(II) and *p*-Benzylsulphonic Acid Azoresorcein (Sodium Salt) (Tropæolin O)

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The composition and stability of palladium(II)-Tropæolin O chelate has been studied by spectrophotometric measurements. The violet-coloured chelate ($\lambda_{\max}$ 520 m μ) has a composition 1:2 (metal : chelating agent). The chelate is stable between pH 2.0 and 5.5. The value of $\log K$ is 0.4 ± 0.1 at 25° (pH 3.5 $\pm$ 0.2). Suggestions have been made about the position of the chelate ring in the metal chelate.

In continuation with our search for new chromogenic reagents for palladium, it has been observed that *p*-benzylsulphonic acid azoresorcein (Na salt) (Tropæolin O) possessing the structure:

forms a violet-coloured chelate with palladium (II) with $\lambda_{\max}$ at 520 m μ between pH 2.0 and 5.5. This reagent in solutions below $10^{-3}M$ appears to be specific for palladium (II). In concentrated solutions it forms reddish orange precipitates with zirconium, thorium, and many rare earths. It was suggested as a gravimetric reagent for zirconium by Popa², who also suggested its possible use for the photometric determination of palladium (II). The composition and stability of the chelate have, however, not been worked out. This communication records our work in this direction.

EXPERIMENTAL

Standard solutions of palladium chloride (B.D.H. reagent) and Tropæolin O (B.D.H. indicator; abbreviated as TPO) were prepared in double distilled water, free from carbon dioxide, and standardised by the usual methods. Other chemicals employed were also of the reagent grade.

Absorbance measurements were carried out with a Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer, as described earlier¹, using 1 cm thickness of the solutions.

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1. Sangal and Dey, this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 464.

2. *Wiss. Z., Friedrich Schiller Univ. Jena, Math. Naturwiss.*, 1960-61, 10, 5.

TABLE I

Composition of Pd-TPO chelate.

Total volume = 50 ml. $pH = 3.5 \pm 0.2$. $p = 1.0$.

Fig. No.	Curve.	c .	λ .	Volume of $PdCl_2$ at peak.	Composition Pd : TPO.
1	A	$1.60 \times 10^{-4}M$	520 $m\mu$	16.7 ml	1 : 2
	B	1.25	520	16.7	1 : 2
	C	1.00	520	16.7	1 : 2
1a*	A	1.66	530	16.7	1 : 2
	B	1.25	530	16.7	1 : 2
	C	1.00	530	16.7	1 : 2

*Figure omitted to economise space.

DISCUSSION

It was ascertained by the method of Vosburgh and Cooper³ that only one chelate is formed in the system under the experimental conditions adopted. The composition of the chelate has been determined by (i) the method of continued variations, (ii) mole-ratio method, and (iii) the slope-ratio method, using absorbance measurements.

Some of the typical results are plotted in Fig. 1. Table I summarises the results on the composition arrived at when the method of continued variations was employed. In the table, c represents the concentration of $PdCl_2$ and p , the ratio c'/c , c' being the concentration of Tropæolin O.

FIG. 1

Table I shows that the ratio of palladium to Tropæolin O in the chelate is 1:2 and hence it may be represented as $Pd(TPO)_2$. Results obtained by the other methods, viz., the mole ratio method and the slope ratio method, corroborate the same composition of the chelate.

The absorbances of mixtures containing $PdCl_2$ and TPO in the ratio 1:2 ($c = 8.0 \times 10^{-5}M$; $c' = 16.0 \times 10^{-5}M$) at different pH 's were measured at various

wave lengths and λ_{max} (520 $m\mu$) of the chelate was found to hold good from pH 2.0 to 5.5, showing the stability of the chelate at this range of pH . The apparent stability constant

was calculated from the absorbance data by the method of Anderson and co-workers⁴, as modified by Dey *et al.*⁵. The value of $\log K$ comes out to be 9.4 ± 0.1 .

The anionic nature of the chelate has been confirmed by electrophoresis studies and also by the complete adsorption of the colour of the complex with the ion-exchange resin, Amberlite IR-45 (OH). The following structure is tentatively suggested for the chelate.

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⁴. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1185; 1945, **71**, 909.

⁵. *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, **6**, 314; *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1958, **18**, 324; *Proc. Symp. Chem. Co-ordination Compounds*, Agra, 1960, vol. 2, p. 199.